

Disposing of Environmental Issues via National Green Tribunal Act, 2010 : A Comment

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Received : 06/02/2021

1st BPR : 18/02/2021

2nd BPR : 28/02/2021

Accepted : 14/03/2021

Abstract

Law Commission of India in its 186th Report, recognized the deficiencies of the existing appellate authorities constituted under various environmental laws and it recommended for setting up of Environmental Courts in each State or for a group of States for exercising all powers of a civil court in its original jurisdiction. As a result, the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010 repealed the preceding two Acts viz. the National Environment Tribunal Act, 1995 and the National Environment Appellate Authority Act, 1997. The main feature of the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010 is that it is not bound by the strict and rigid rules of procedural laws, and its decisions are based on the sound principles of natural justice. In this paper, the evaluation of the working of the Green Tribunal has been done through some cases, including also the scheme and objects of the Act.

Keywords: Environmental Court, The National Green Tribunal, Principles of Natural Justice

Introduction

On request of the Supreme Court, Law Commission of India in its 186th Report, recognized the deficiencies of the existing appellate authorities constituted under various environmental laws, and it recommended for setting up of environmental courts in each State or for a group of States for exercising all powers of a Civil Court in its original jurisdiction. The National Green Tribunal Act, 2010 repealed the preceding two Acts viz. the National Environment Tribunal Act, 1995 and the National Environment Appellate Authority Act, 1997. The main feature of this Act is that it is not bound by the strict rules of procedure and its decisions are based on the sound principles of natural justice.

Background of the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010

Section 38 of the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010 comprises the provision for the repeal of the National Environment Tribunal Act, 1995 and the National Environment Appellate Authority Act, 1997. Furthermore, it provides that notwithstanding such repeal, anything done or any action taken under these Acts shall be deemed to have been done or taken under the corresponding provisions of the present legislation. Thus, the National Environment Authority established under Section 3(1) of the National Environment Appellate Tribunal Act, 1997 stands dissolved and all cases pending before it shall be transferred to the National Green Tribunal.

In order to provide speedy disposal of cases regarding compensation arising out of strict liability, and to ensure the safeguards provided under the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986, both aforesaid Acts (one of National Tribunal and second of Appellate Authority) were passed; but both of these Acts could not succeed as they had only narrow jurisdiction to deal with rising environmental issues and cases. Therefore, Supreme Court felt the urgent and dire need of such an environment-related law as would effectively deal with all the civil matters relating to environmental issues well within its original jurisdiction and at the same time deal with appellate judicial powers against orders passed by the concerned authorities under the **Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974**, the **Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981**, the **Environment (Protection) Act, 1986** and the **Public Liability Insurance Act, 1991**. Hence, the National Green Tribunal Bill was passed in Indian Parliament by both the houses. After being assented to by the President on June 2nd, 2010, it came into force on 18.10.2010.⁽¹⁾

The positive feature about this Act is that it is not bound by the rigid rules of procedure, and basing the decisions of this Green Tribunal has been conceived on the sound principles of Natural Justice.

Scope of National Green Tribunal Act, 2010

This Act comprises the jurisdiction over all civil cases where substantial question relating to environment is involved, and which includes enforcement of any legal right relating to environment. Such question should arise out of the implementation of the enactments specified in the Schedule I of the Act and to grant relief and compensation to the victims of pollution and other environmental damage arising under the enactments specified in the Schedule I of the Act, and also to hear appeals under certain enactments specified in the Schedule III of the Act.

Scheme of the Act

This Act of Green Tribunal comprises of 38 sections in five chapters division, and contains three Schedules also. Chapter I contains two sections. Section 1 contains short title, Commencement, enforcement etc. Section 2 of the Act provides some **relevant definitions**⁽²⁾, namely a) 'Accident', c) 'Environment' e) 'Handling', f) 'Hazardous Substance', g) 'Injury', m) 'Substantial question relating to Environment', and n) 'Tribunal' etc. Before proceeding further, giving definitions of the following words and expressions are necessary –

As per **Section 2(a) 'Accident'** means an accident involving a fortuitous or sudden or unintended occurrence while handling any hazardous substance or equipment, or plant, or vehicle resulting in continuous or intermittent or repeated exposure to death, of, or, injury to, any person or damage to any property or environment but does not include an accident by reason only of war or civil disturbance.

Section (c) 'Environment' includes water, air and land and the interrelationship, which exists among and between water, air and land and human beings, other living creatures, plants, micro-organism and property.

Section 2(f) 'Hazardous Substance' means any substance or preparation which is defined as hazardous substance in the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 be specified by the Central Government under the Public Liability Insurance Act, 1991.

Section 2(g) 'Injury' includes permanent, partial or total disablement or sickness resulting out of an accident.

Section 2(m) 'Substantial question relating to environment' shall include an instance where –

- i) There is a direct violation of a specific statutory environment obligation by a person by which –
 - A) The community at large other than an individual or group of individuals is affected or likely to be affected by the environmental consequences; or
 - B) The gravity of damage to the environment or property is substantial; or
 - C) The damage to public health is broadly measurable.
- ii) The environmental consequences relate to a specific activity or a point source of pollution.

Section 2(n) 'Tribunal' means the National Green Tribunal established under Section 3.

Objectives of the Act

Indian Parliament passed the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010 to realize the following objectives –

- i) Providing for effective and expeditious disposal of cases relating to environmental protection;
- ii) Providing for conservation of forests and other natural resources including enforcement of any legal right relating to environment;
- iii) Providing for giving relief and compensation for damages to persons and property;
- iv) To repeal the 'National Environment Tribunal Act, 1995' and the 'National Environment Appellate Authority Act', 1997; and
- v) To deal with matters connected therewith or incidental thereto.

Composition of the National Green Tribunal

Section 3 of the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010 establishes the National Green Tribunal (NGT) which is a specialized court, and chiefly to be governed by the high principles of Natural Justice, and not necessarily bound by the rigid procedural laws. Section 4 of this Act gives the composition of the Tribunal as under and shall consist of –

- a) A full time chair person;
- b) Not less than ten but subject to maximum of twenty full time Judicial Members as the Central Government may from time to time notify.

- c) Not less than ten but subject to maximum of twenty full time expert Members, as the Central Government may from time to time.

The Chairperson may also constitute a Bench of two or more members consisting of at least one Judicial Member and one Expert Member. The Chairperson shall also have the power to decide the distribution of the business of the Tribunal amongst the members of the Tribunal sitting at different places and specify the matters which may be dealt with by each such sitting.

Chairperson, Judicial Member and Expert Member : Their Qualification

Section 5 of the Act says that 'a person shall be qualified for appointment as a Chairperson if he – (1) is, or has been, a Judge of the Supreme Court of India; or (2) Chief Justice of a High Court.

A person shall be qualified for appointment as a Judicial Member if he : (1) is, or has been, a judge of the Supreme Court of India; or (2) Chief Justice of a High Court; or (3) is, or has been, a Judge of the High Court.

A person shall be qualified for appointment as an Expert member if he : (1) has a degree in Master of Science (in Physical Sciences or Life Sciences with a Doctorate degree of Master of Engineering or Master of Technology and has an experience of fifteen years in the relevant field including five years practical experience in the field of environment and forests (including pollution control, hazardous substance management, environment, climate-change management, biological diversity management and forest conservation) in a reputed National Level Institution; or (2) has administrative experience of fifteen years including experience of five years in dealing with environmental matters in the Central or a State Government or in a reputed National or State level institution.

Jurisdiction of the National Green Tribunal

As per Section 14 of this Act, the Tribunal shall have jurisdiction in all civil matters where substantial question relating to environment is involved including enforcement of any legal right relating to environment arising as follows : (i) Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974; (ii) Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Cess Act, 1977; (iii) Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980; (iv) Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981; (v) Environment (Protection) Act, 1991, and also (vi) Bio-Diversity Act, 2002.

In one case⁽³⁾, Supreme Court observed that the environmental issues covered under the National Green Tribunal Act Schedule I should be instituted and litigated before the National Green Tribunal. This approach is necessary to avoid likelihood of conflict of orders between the High Court and National Green Tribunal. The National Green Tribunal Constituted under the NGT Act, 2010 has been given extensive powers to award compensation and grant relief in deciding cases.

Appeal to the Supreme Court and the Other Matters

Per Section 22, an appeal against the decision of the NGT shall lie to the Supreme Court. As regards the Execution of order/award or decision of the Tribunal shall be executable by the Tribunal just like a decree of a civil court. Sec. 26 also provides that wherever fails to comply with its decisions, order or award shall be punishable either with imprisonment (term extendable to three years); or Fine (extended to ten/crore rupees); or with both. As regards, Bar of Jurisdiction, Sec. 29 of the NGT Act bars the jurisdiction of the civil courts in terms of Appeal, the settlement or entertaining any question relating to claim for relief, compensation or restitution of property damaged or environment damaged.

As per Section 31, the Chairperson, the Judicial and Expert Members shall be deemed to be public servants within the ambit of Sec. 21 of the Indian Penal Code, 1860. No suit, prosecution or other legal proceedings shall lie against right from Chairperson to all other officials, members and any person authorized by the Chairperson, Judicial member or the Expert member for anything which is in good faith done or intended to be done in pursuance of this Act or any rule or order made thereunder. In addition, this Act shall have overriding effect, notwithstanding anything inconsistent contained in other law or instrument.

The Power of the Central Government to amend the Schedule I is there by which it may, by notification, include therein anything, with regard to the objective of environmental protection and conservation of natural resources.

Evaluating the Role of National Green Tribunal As A Specialized Environment Court

The National Green Tribunal was established on 31st January 2015 under Section 3 of this Act. Right from the auspicious start of this Act, the National Green Tribunal (hereinafter NGT), has been implementing its dominant role in the cases of environment related issues. Its working experience has been on issues that are multidisciplinary in nature relating to Environment Protection and ensuring hygienic and healthy environmental right to the citizens of India. This is well illustrated in the following cases –

In **Mr. Asim Sarode and Others Vs. Maharashtra Pollution Control Board and Others**⁽⁴⁾, the question of unscientific and unauthorized burning of tyres that emit smoke having toxic gases and pollutants affecting the human life as well as environment. The NGT realizing the urgent need to regulate the used tyre disposal to avoid the environmental damage applied the principles of sustainable development and precautionary principles. Thus, the Tribunal banned the burning of tyres in open areas and at public places looking to the gravity of air pollution and its resultant health implications.

In **B.L. Mishra Vs. The Collective Chhattarpur and Others**⁽⁵⁾, the Tribunal directed that no untreated sewage from the surrounding area was allowed to flow into the Kishore Sagar Lake, and the State Pollution Control Board was also directed to make sure that the quality of water of the Lake be regularly monitored.

In **Sanjay Kumar Vs. Union of India**⁽⁶⁾, the NGT directed the Delhi Government to demolish all permanent and temporary illegal structures built by Sant Sri Asa Ramji Bapu Trust in Karol Bagh.

In **Save Mon Region Federation and Ors. Vs. Union of India**⁽⁷⁾, this is specifically noteworthy from legal interpretation perspective, where the Tribunal observed that due to lack of knowledge about the grant of Environmental Clearance, concerned citizens and groups are unable to file an appeal before the NGT on time. In this case NGT took strong exception to lack of transparency in MoEF specifically with respect to its website. So, the judgment here is a strong step towards making all-out efforts to ensure greater access to environmental information and the remedy of appeal is made effective, and at the same time any obstacles in form of limitation or narrow legal interpretation will be discouraged in attaining sound and meaningful Environmental Justice.

Thus, we witness from the above mentioned cases that the newly formed Tribunal conceived and established under National Green Tribunal will hopefully go a long-long way in mitigating environmental problems and issues and ensuring its noble objective of providing healthy environment to the people of India.

References

1. The National Green Tribunal (NGT) as a specialized Court established u/s 3 by the Central Government (vide S.O. 2570 (E), dated 18th Oct, 2010).
2. Section 2 of the National Green Tribunal, 2010
3. Bhopal Gas Peedith Mahila Udyog Sangathan Vs. Union of India [(2012) 8 SCC 326 at 347]
4. Application No. 43/2013 (Western Zone Bench, Pune)
5. [Original Application No. 22/2013 (order dated 7th August 2014, Central Zonal Bench Bhopal)]
6. [Original Application No. 306 of 2013 (Principal Bench, New Delhi)]
7. [M.A. 104 of 2012 (Principal Bench, N. Delhi)]

